

PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT IN LITERACY DEVELOPMENT AMONG KINDERGARTENERS: BASIS FOR STRENGTHENING READING PROGRAMS FOR BEGINNING LEARNERS

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Parental Involvement in Literacy Development among Kindergarteners: Basis for Strengthening Reading Programs for Beginning Learners

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Abstract

This study explored parental involvement in the literacy development of kindergarteners, employing an ex post facto expository research design to assess how specific parental characteristics impact children's literacy engagement. A stratified sampling technique was used to select 40 parents—20 females and 20 males—from various public schools within the Umingan II District, ensuring diverse representation of experiences and perspectives. Data were gathered through a validated questionnaire checklist, which consisted of two parts: the demographic profile of respondents and their level of involvement in various literacy components, such as alphabet knowledge, phonological awareness, and vocabulary development. Findings indicate that most respondent parents have a secondary education level, a family income between P5,000 to P10,000, and a limited number of reading materials at home. The overall level of parental involvement in literacy development is rated as "Moderately Involved," with significant differences observed in involvement based on educational attainment, income, and availability of reading materials. Conclusions suggest that variations in parental profiles significantly affect involvement levels, and that a lack of resources contributes to moderate engagement. Recommendations emphasize the importance of enhancing vocabulary development, establishing dedicated time for literacy activities at home, fostering collaboration with teachers, and seeking partnerships for increased access to reading materials. The study highlights the need for further research into the broader aspects of parental involvement in literacy development among kindergarteners.

Keywords: *parental involvement, strengthening, programs, reading*

Introduction

Parental involvement contributes to improving learners' achievement, especially in literacy (Silinkas et al., 2012). This may contribute to positive social change by providing helpful information that can assist schools and teachers in developing effective strategies for encouraging parental involvement for families with children in kindergarten, which may close reading gaps.

Researchers have shown a literacy gap as students enter school, which may be attributed to issues of educational preparation (Powell et al., 2012; Snell et al., 2015; Waldfozel 2012). Kindergarten learners' progress and success depend on variable reading preparation and educational experiences after entering school. Moreover, parents have a role in the level of involvement by beginning children's informal education at home (Belton & Cook, 2012; Silinkas et al., 2012; Wald Fozel). Children who have experienced good quality early informal education (i.e., learning at home before they start school, i.e., learning in the classroom tend to become more capable of faster literacy improvement after enrolling in formal schooling (Duke 2012, Maguire, Hirsh Parek Golinkofy and Brandon 2008; Silinkas et al., 2012; Snell et al., 2015).

To sustain further the literacy program, DepEd Order no. 1, s.2024 discusses that Catch-Up Fridays will be held every Fridays to help address learning gaps through focused instruction on reading, values education, health education and peace education. This weekly learning intervention that requires schools to dedicate half of the day to reading activities and other half for values, health and peace education. Hence the need of parental involvement.

DepEd Order No. 173, series of 2019, highlights the importance of parental involvement in the educational process, emphasizing the need for effective partnerships among parents, schools, and communities. This order aims to create an inclusive learning environment where families are encouraged to play an active role in their children's education. Additionally, earlier policies such as DepEd Order No. 47, series of 2016, promote active parental engagement in school activities, and DepEd Order No. 5, series of 2012, outlines strategies for enhancing parent-teacher partnerships. Together, these directives provide a robust framework for fostering parental involvement and enhancing literacy programs aimed at beginning learners.

Parents' involvement in literacy benefits learners' social, cognitive, and mental capacities (Hornty & Whittle, 2010; Nitech, 2015). When parents actively engage in their child's education, learners increase their learning by actively engaging in their education, utilizing learning objectives, and achieving measurable growth and outcomes (Marshall & Jackman, 2015).

Parent involvement connects the parent to the child, teacher administration, and school in a special relationship that builds community and supports learning outcomes, especially in public schools. Parent involvement in the schools is a shared responsibility in which schools and other agencies and organizations are committed to engaging parents in meaningful ways, and parents are committed to actively supporting their children in learning and environment.

Parent involvement is especially critical in kindergarten because it is a transition for children and their parents and because success in kindergarten has direct connections to academic success in future grades and learning for life. Nelson (2005) asserted, "A child's success

in kindergarten is a strong predictor of future school success. Children with parental support also enter kindergarten not only ready to learn but also with a developed maturity, allowing them to adapt to the new kindergarten classroom environment. Children need school and parental support from home to transition successfully into kindergarten.

Moreover, parents' involvement in early literacy is directly connected to academic achievement. Children need parents to be their reading models with daily practice to successfully navigate through beginning literacy skills. According to research, parents should focus on the words on the page while reading to their children (Evans et al., 2000).

In the Schools District of Umingan II, teachers connect with parents to gain support in implementing the literacy program. The schools conducted different activities, like orientation and simulation, to encourage parents to gain support in literacy development among young learners.

In this premise, the researcher aims to determine the level of parental involvement in literacy development among kindergartens focusing on alphabet knowledge, phonological awareness, print concepts, words and patterns, vocabulary, and language development and to prepare some activities to strengthen reading programs for beginning learners.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the level of parental involvement in literacy development among kindergarteners in the District of Umingan II, school year 2024-2025. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. highest educational attainment;
 - 1.2. occupation;
 - 1.3. monthly income;
 - 1.4. number of children; and
 - 1.5. number of reading materials at home
2. What is the level of parental involvement literacy development among kindergarteners along:
 - 2.1. alphabet knowledge;
 - 2.2. phonological awareness;
 - 2.3. print concepts;
 - 2.4. words and patterns;
 - 2.5. vocabulary; and
 - 2.6. language development?
3. Is there a significant difference in the level of parental involvement in literacy development among kindergarteners across their profile variables?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of parental involvement in literacy development among kindergarteners and their profile variables?

Methodology

Research Design

The research design is the foundational framework that shapes the entire research endeavor. It encompasses critical elements such as selecting suitable research methods, strategies for data collection, sampling methodologies, and approaches to data analysis. As Somasundaram (2022) highlighted, establishing a well-defined research design is paramount for maintaining consistency, logic, and alignment with the research questions and objectives. This, in turn, ensures the accuracy, reliability, and relevance of the study's results. In this study, the ex post facto expository research design was used. This research design, also known as "after-the-fact" research, is a research design that looks into how an independent group (groups with certain qualities that already exist prior to the study) affects a dependent variable. The ex post facto approach is centered on uncovering the cause-and-effect connection between a variable that depends on another and the independent variable. The independent variable, however, cannot be manipulated or altered, so ex post facto studies will look at how a particular characteristic trait or past occurrence affects the dependent variable.

On the other hand, the researcher employed the descriptive research methodology, aligning with the nature of the research problems presented.

The insights from Sirisilla (2023) underscore the essence of a descriptive research design, emphasizing its primary objective of observing and collecting information on a specific subject without attempting to establish cause-and-effect relationships. This research approach is geared towards characterizing relationships, patterns, and trends within the data, with the overarching goal of providing a comprehensive and accurate portrayal of the population or phenomenon being investigated.

Similarly, Neumann (2020) stated that descriptive research is a type of study design that aims to answer questions about how a situation arises, when it occurs in terms of time or date, where it occurs in terms of location, and what the problem or phenomenon is. The primary goal of the research design is to provide a more thorough understanding of the population; as a result, it successfully

incorporates various research techniques, including surveys, observational studies, and case studies. It is a special design because the researcher measures the results by observation rather than changing the variable.

Descriptive research is a systematic method for gathering, analyzing, categorizing, and recording data related to current conditions, methodologies, principles, behaviors, developments, and the interplay of cause and effect. This approach is geared towards making thorough and precise data analyses, which may or may not include statistical techniques for support.

In this particular investigation, the researcher utilized descriptive research framework to examine and interpret the level of parental involvement in sustaining learners' engagement in blended learning in the District of Umingan II. The statistical analysis results were the basis for inferences, conclusions, and recommendations.

Respondents

The researcher employed a stratified sampling technique in this study to determine the number of participants. This method, called proportional or quota random sampling, involves dividing the overall population into uniform groups, or strata, to facilitate the sampling effort. For this study, a group of 40 parents whom 20 are females and 20 are males from various public schools within the Umingan II District were selected as the sample.

Choosing participants from various public schools across the district enabled a wide-ranging representation, embracing a more extensive array of experiences and viewpoints pertinent to the study's goals.

Using stratified sampling to determine the respondents allows for a more practical and feasible approach to data collection. It simplifies the logistics of reaching participants and is particularly beneficial in educational research, where resources and time constraints may limit the ability to survey every family member of learners within the division.

Instrument

The researcher utilized a questionnaire checklist as the main tool for gathering data for this study. This checklist consisted of a formal list of questions used to collect information from the respondents. A checklist format was employed to ensure that all pertinent data was recorded.

The questionnaire checklist was constructed after a comprehensive search of related literature and studies regarding parental involvement. After which it will be validated by experts. This approach ensures the questions are well-informed, relevant, and comprehensive, enabling the researcher to gather the necessary data effectively.

The questionnaire checklist consisted of two (2) parts. Part I focused on the demographic profile of the respondent teachers, such as age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, financial status, and occupation. Meanwhile, Part II included the level of parental involvement in literacy development among kindergarteners along alphabet knowledge, phonological awareness, print concepts, words and patterns, vocabulary and language development.

Research experts evaluated, refined, and improved the questionnaire checklist using the Survey/ Validation Rubric for Expert Panel by Simon & White (2016) (See appendix B). Five (5) experts validated the questionnaire checklist namely: (1) female Education Program Supervisor in charge of kindergarten, (1) male District Supervisor, (1) male Principal, (1) female Master Teacher handling kindergarten, and (1) female President of SPTA. The objective of the validation was to ensure that every question would be clearly understood and within the respondents' experience. This was also to ensure that the respondents could answer the questionnaire and that the data gathered would be valid. The suggestions were incorporated in the final draft. The questionnaire checklist was finalized after its approval.

Procedure

Once the questionnaire checklist was refined and finalized, the researcher secured a permit to conduct the study from the Office of the Public Schools District Supervisor of Umingan District II, SDO II of Pangasinan. This permit ensured that the study was approved and complied with ethical guidelines and procedures.

After securing the permit, the researcher personally administered the questionnaire to the respondents. The researcher handed out the surveys to the participants, clarifying the study's objectives and significance to motivate their involvement. After the respondents had answered the questionnaires, the researcher retrieved the questionnaires to ensure that all the necessary data had been captured. The researcher analyzed and interpreted all the data gathered utilizing the research instrument.

Data Analysis

Following the completion of the questionnaire checklist and data collection, the researcher tabulated, organized, sorted, and total the data into an Excel spreadsheet. This ensured the data is properly structured and errors or inconsistencies can be identified and corrected. The data collected were subjected to treatment using appropriate statistical tools.

To answer problem number 1 on the profile of the respondents in terms of highest educational attainment, occupation, monthly income, number of children, and number of reading materials, the researcher utilized frequency counts and percentages. Each profile variable

was categorized and assigned a corresponding numerical value to facilitate computation.

To answer problem number 2 on the level of parental involvement in literacy development among kindergarteners along alphabet knowledge, phonological awareness, print concepts, words and patterns and language development, the weighted mean was utilized and interpreted.

To answer Problem No. 3, the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and t-test were used to determine the significant difference in the level of parental involvement in literacy development among kindergarteners across their profile variables.

In the case that the F-statistic is statistically significant, indicating that there is a significant difference between the means of the groups, Scheffe test will be employed to determine which specific groups differ from each other.

To answer Problem No. 4 on determining the relationship between the level of parental involvement in literacy development among kindergarteners and the profile variables, the Coded Pearson Product Correlation was used.

A positive correlation coefficient indicates a positive relationship, while a negative correlation coefficient indicates a negative relationship. The absolute value of the correlation coefficient indicates the strength of the relationship, with higher absolute values indicating stronger relationships.

However, it is important to note that correlation does not imply causation. Therefore, even if a strong relationship is found between the level of parental involvement in sustaining learners' engagement in blended learning and a profile variable, it does not necessarily mean that one variable causes the other.

Ethical Considerations

Letters were distributed to the respondents to request their permission for participation in the study. In instances where respondents will opt not to provide their responses, their decision will be acknowledged with respect and consideration. It is crucial to highlight that the researcher took measures to guarantee the utmost confidentiality and privacy of all collected data, prioritizing the protection of the participants' anonymity.

Results and Discussion

Profile of the Respondents

The respondents' profile provides and describes the background information about them as subject of the study. Such profile variables were likewise used to describe and analyze the relationships between the level of parental involvement in literacy development among kindergarten learners and their profile variables. Table 1 shows the profile of the respondents.

Table 1. *Profile of the Respondents*

<i>Profile Variables</i>	<i>Variable Category</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>
Sex	Female	20	50.0
	Male	20	50.0
Highest Educational Attainment	Elementary graduate	3	7.5
	Grades 7 to 10	20	50.0
	SHS Graduate	3	7.5
	College Undergraduate	6	15.0
	College Graduate	8	20.0
Occupation	Tutor	2	5.0
	Teacher	6	15.0
	House Wife	11	27.5
	Farmer	12	30.0
	Store Owner	3	7.5
	Guard	3	7.5
	Driver	3	7.5
	Tutor	2	5.0
	Family Monthly Income	less than 5000	18
5000-10000		13	32.5
11000-15000		3	7.5
15000-20000		2	5.0
25000-30000		2	5.0
30000-35000		2	5.0
Number of Children	1-2	23	57.5
	3-5	17	42.5
Number of Reading Materials at Home	1-5	19	47.5
	6-10	14	35.0
	11-15	5	12.5
	16-20	2	5.0

Sex. In terms of sex, both categories have 20 respondents each that is 20 or 50 percent are females while 20 or 50 percent also are males. This could mean that there are equal number of respondents in the locale of the study.

Highest Educational Attainment. As reflected in the table, most of the respondents have attained Grade 7-10 that is 50 percent, 8 or 20 percent are college undergraduate while 3 or 7.5 percent are both elementary and senior high school graduates. This could be interpreted to mean that very few respondents have attained the highest level of education while the rest just obtained some levels in the basic education.

Occupation. It can be seen in the table that the respondents perform different jobs. Most of them are farmers that is 12 or 30 percent, 11 or 27.5 percent are housekeepers, 6 or 15 percent are teachers while 3 or 7.5 percent are store owners same with guards and drivers while 2 or 5 percent are tutors. This could mean that the respondents have simple jobs that could support their families.

Monthly Income. The data on the respondents' monthly income show that the majority, 45%, earn less than 5000 pesos per month, indicating that nearly half of the respondents are in the lower income bracket. Additionally, 32.5% of the respondents have a monthly income between 5000 and 10000 pesos, bringing the total to 77.5% of respondents who earn 10000 pesos or less. A smaller portion, 7.5%, reports earning between 11000 and 15000 pesos, while 5% each fall into the income brackets of 15000-20000 pesos, 25000-30000 pesos, and 30000-35000 pesos. Based on the income distribution of the respondents and referencing the National Economic and Development Researcherity (NEDA) standards, a significant portion of the respondents fall within the lower-income bracket. According to NEDA, households with a monthly income below 10,000 pesos are often categorized as low-income, with many potentially living at or below the poverty line, especially in rural areas or regions with higher living costs. In this case, 77.5% of the respondents earn 10,000 pesos or less, suggesting that the majority may face economic challenges and limitations in accessing resources.

Number of Children. The data on the number of children among the respondents show that the majority, 57.5%, have between 1 to 2 children, while 42.5% have between 3 to 5 children. This indicates that a greater portion of the respondents tend to have smaller families with 1 to 2 children, though a significant number still have larger families with 3 to 5 children. The cumulative percentage confirms that all respondents fall within these two categories, and no respondents reported having more than 5 children or no children at all. This distribution reflects a tendency toward smaller family sizes, though larger families remain common. Further, this could also mean that the respondents implemented the family planning program of the government considering of the few number of children that they have in the family.

Number of Reading Materials at Home. The data on the number of reading materials at home reveals that nearly half of the respondents (47.5%) have between 1 to 5 reading materials, making this the most common range. In addition, 35% of respondents have 6 to 10 reading materials, which brings the cumulative total to 82.5% of households with 10 or fewer reading resources. A smaller portion, 12.5%, have 11 to 15 reading materials, while only 5% have between 16 and 20 reading materials.

This distribution suggests that while many respondents have access to some reading materials at home, a significant number have a limited collection, with most households having fewer than 10 items. This could point to potential challenges in fostering a reading-rich environment, especially in homes with fewer educational resources.

Level Of Parental Involvement In Literacy Development Among Kindergarteners

The main purpose of this study is to determine the level of parental involvement in literacy development among kindergarteners in alphabet knowledge, phonological awareness, print concepts, language development, vocabulary and words and patterns. The results of which will serve as basis for strengthening reading program for beginning readers.

Table 2 presents the level of parental involvement in literacy development among kindergarteners along alphabet knowledge.

Table 2. *Level of Parental Involvement in Literacy Development among Kindergarteners along Alphabet Knowledge*

<i>Alphabet Knowledge</i>		<i>WM</i>	<i>TR</i>
<i>As a parent, I involve myself in literacy development by</i>			
1.	presenting letters as I play with my child with alphabet blocks	3.08	MI
2.	using everyday items to create an alphabet chart	2.53	MI
3.	playing letter sound games	2.98	MI
4.	introducing new letters in a regular basis	2.80	MI
5.	using songs and rhymes	3.25	MI
6.	encouraging them to write their own letters	3.13	MI
7.	teaching letter names then letter words	3.23	MI
8.	introducing simple sounds then complex	2.83	MI
9.	adjusting pace according to my child's needs	3.03	MI
10.	providing hands on and multi-sensory activities	2.85	MI
OWM		2.97	MI

Legend: 4.50-5.00 – Highly Involved (HI); 3.50-4.49 - Involved (I); 2.50-3.49 - Moderately Involved (MI); 1.50-2.49 - Slightly Involved (SI); 1.00-1.49 - Not Involved (NI)

The table shows that the respondent parents have a “Moderately Involved” transmuted rating in their level of parental involvement in literacy development among kindergarteners as signified by themselves with an overall weighted mean of 2.97. This could mean that the parents involvement in the literacy development of the young learners in alphabet knowledge is somewhat considerable due to their willingness to help their children read, relieving that education is the only legacy they can offer their children.

It is also noted that all the ten (10) indicators were rated “Moderately Involved” with weighted means that range from 2.53 to 3.25. The fair involvement of parents in literacy development along alphabet knowledge would imply that parents try their best to make their children learn better each day so that play alphabet blocks, create alphabet chart and encourage them to write their own letters which is one way of mastering the letters of the alphabet which are the foundation of all words.

According to Cheung (2019), learning the alphabet is a foundational-skills in reading. If children don’t understand printed symbols on page, they cannot read words and unlock their meaning. Moreover, the National Early Literacy Panels report in 2008 concluded that learning the alphabet was the number 1 predictor of the future reading success. As such, parental involvement is needed. Parental involvement motivates children to learn, leading to higher grades. The level of parental involvement is crucial in producing high impact on the learners’ performance. It is said that the higher degree of parental involvement, the higher impact on the child’s academic performance.

In the same vein, Delgado (2022), learning the alphabet isn’t just about reading; it also plays a critical role in cognitive development. Think of the alphabet as building blocks for the brain. As children engage with letters and sounds, their brain forms connections and pathways that lay the foundations for further learning and cognitive skills.

Fajujo (2015) stressed that parental involvement in literacy development is very important. Parents need to be aware of the importance of developing this skills at a young age. Parents may believe they do not have the knowledge to work with their children on literacy, but they have a wealth of knowledge from their backgrounds and cultures that can benefit their child. And this would imply that they can help their children on alphabet knowledge by presenting letter with alphabet blocks, suing everyday items to create an alphabet chart, play letter sounds games and use toys to help reinforce letter sounds.

Table 3 presents the level of parental involvement in literacy development among kindergarteners along phonological awareness.

Table 3. *Level of Parental Involvement in Literacy Development among Kindergarteners along Phonological Awareness*

<i>Phonological awareness</i>		<i>WM</i>	<i>TR</i>
<i>As a parent, I involve myself in literacy development by</i>			
1.	focusing on rhyming word	2.95	MI
2.	following the beat	2.88	MI
3.	carrying tune	2.58	MI
4.	correcting the sounds	3.18	MI
5.	getting into guess word	2.65	MI
6.	listening up	3.03	MI
7.	getting creative with crafts	2.55	MI
8.	connecting the sounds	2.85	MI
9.	breaking apart words	2.75	MI
10.	reading aloud regularly	2.90	MI
OWM		2.83	MI

Legend: 4.50-5.00 – Highly Involved (HI); 3.50-4.49 - Involved (I); 2.50-3.49 - Moderately Involved (MI); 1.50-2.49 Slightly Involved (SI); 1.00-1.49 - Not Involved (NI)

As shown in the table, the parents signified that they have a “Moderately Involved” transmuted rating regarding their involvement in literacy development along phonological awareness with an overall weighted mean of 2.83. This would imply that parents fairly involved themselves in helping their children in phonological awareness and this could be attributed to their educational attainment considering that most of them have attained secondary basic education. As such, their limited knowledge can be considered a factor of not fully involving themselves in helping their children in phonological awareness. It is surprising to note that all the ten indicators were rated “Moderately Involved” with weighted means that range from 3.18 to 2.55 of which item no. 4 “hunt alphabet letters” obtained the highest rating of 3.18 while indicator no. 7 “get creative with crafts” obtained the lowest with a weighted mean of 2.55. This could be interpreted to mean that the parents are fun of involving themselves in hunting alphabet letters considering that its an interesting activity for their children. On the other hand, they are fair in involving themselves in getting creative crafts due to the inadequacy of learning materials at home.

Moats (2019) stressed that phonological awareness is essential for reading because written words correspond to spoken words. As such children must have awareness of the speech sounds that letters and letter combinations represent in order to move from a printed word to a spoken words (reading) or spoken word to a written words (spelling).

Moreover, Pinquart (2015), pointed out that children whose families are engaged in their education are more likely to learn better, develop their self-confidence and highly motivated in the classroom. Likewise, parents who involved themselves in teaching their children phonological and phonemic awareness are likely to develop their children the ability to hear, identify and play with sounds in

spoken language including rhymes, syllables and the smallest units of sounds.

Table 4 presents the level of parental involvement in literacy development among kindergarteners along print concepts.

As reflected in the table, the level of parental involvement in literacy development among kindergarteners along print concepts obtained an overall weighted mean of 2.81 denoting a “Moderately Involved” transmuted rating. The fair involvement of parents in this area could be attributed to the inadequacy of reading materials at home considering that not all parents can avail of the different reading materials due to financial constraints.

Table 4. *Level of Parental Involvement in Literacy Development among Kindergarteners along Print Concepts*

	<i>Print Concepts</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>TR</i>
<i>As a parent, I involve myself in literacy development by</i>			
1.	building a print rich environment	2.93	MI
2.	sorting letter and number	3.15	MI
3.	making words	2.78	MI
4.	hunting alphabet letters	2.93	MI
5.	building sentences	2.78	MI
6.	using book walls	2.38	MI
7.	helping my child understand that written words just as spoken words	2.95	MI
8.	using stories that have predictable words in the text	2.73	MI
9.	using big books and draw attention to words and letters	2.73	MI
10.	utilizing environmental print to make reference to word spaces, letters and line points	2.75	MI
		OWM	2.81 MI

Legend: 4.50-5.00 – Highly Involved (HI); 3.50-4.49 - Involved (I); 2.50-3.49 - Moderately Involved (MI); 1.50-2.49 - Slightly Involved (SI); 1.00-1.49 - Not Involved (NI)

It is interesting to note that all the ten indicators obtained a transmuted rating of “Moderately Involved” having weighted means that range from 2.38 to 3.15 where item no. 2 “sort letter and number” got the highest rating while item no. 6 “use book walls” obtained the lowest rating. This could be interpreted to mean that parents are familiar with sorting letter and number so they can help more their children on this particular skill in print concepts. On the contrary, using book walls are not familiar with parents, hence the low rating.

The need of parents involvement in literacy development along print concepts is highly encouraged. According to Durisic (2021), print concepts are rules readers follow in order to be able to read successfully. Building an awareness of these concepts such as how to hold a book, books have front and back covers, pages are turned from left top right and that letters make up words is crucial to learning to read. Moreover, concepts of prints lead to the recognition of symbols and letter shapes. Once their understanding is established, the letter shapes can be associated with sounds connecting the visual auditing and oral systems.

In the same vein, Cheung (2019) stressed that the knowledge that printed words carry meaning and that reading and writing are ways to get ideas and information pave the way to the literacy development of the child, through print texts improves comprehension more that reading digital materials does according to him.

Moreover, Altinoz (2019) pointed out also that print awareness helps a child understand that written words communicate just as spoken words do that you can say the words that are written down. Understanding the components of print is critical for early literacy because it allows learners to form essential concepts of print which are vital.

Table 5 provides the level of parental involvement in literacy development among kindergarteners along language development.

Table 5. *Level of Parental Involvement in Literacy Development among Kindergarteners along Language Development*

	<i>Language Development</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>TR</i>
<i>As a parent, I involve myself in literacy development by</i>			
1.	talking with the child use different words in different context	3.10	MI
2.	responding to my child’s attempts to communicate	3.28	MI
3.	reading with my child	3.13	MI
4.	using specific labels to object	2.65	MI
5.	modeling good spoken language	3.05	MI
6.	helping extend my child language learning by adding a word or an idea to what he says	3.10	MI
7.	talking together with my child about things that interest her the most	3.40	MI
8.	expanding my child’s vocabulary with word games	2.75	MI
9.	using tongue twisters to foster good communication skill of my child	2.73	MI
10.	utilizing riddles, rhymes, songs and story telling to help my child develop his language	2.85	MI
		OWM	3.00 MI

Legend: 4.50-5.00 – Highly Involved (HI); 3.50-4.49 - Involved (I); 2.50-3.49 - Moderately Involved (MI); 1.50-2.49 - Slightly Involved (SI); 1.00-1.49 - Not Involved (NI)

As shown in the table, the respondent parents signified that they are “Moderately Involved” in literacy development of their children along language development with an overall weighted mean of 3.00. The result would imply that they fairly consider their involvement

in this are considering that most of them have attended secondary education levels and their experience in teaching their children in developing language is very limited. Although they can also respond to the needs of their children in the simplest manner by modeling good spoken language that can help their children language learning by adding a word or an idea to what they say. They also practice talking together with their children about things that give them interest which could lead to language development.

Further, all the ten indicators have a corresponding transmuted rating of “Moderately Involved” with weighted means that range from 2.65 to 3.40 where indicator no. 7 “talking together with my child about things that interest him the most” obtained the highest rating while item no. 4 “use specific labels to objects” got the lowest ratings. This could mean that the parents are familiar with the approach of talking together with their children about the things that give interest in developing language considering that is the easiest way of helping their children in developing their language skills. On the other hand, using specific labels to objects in developing the language of the child is frequently used by the parents and this can be attributed to the inadequacy of objects that they have at home especially the objects that they use everyday for the reason that most of the parents are below the poverty line threshold by the NEDA.

Bartolome et al. (2018) stressed that parental involvement are in direly need in the language development of the child. In fact, the amount and style of language that aprents use when convening with their children is one of the strongest predictions of children’s early language. Children benefit from exposure to adult speech that is varied and rich in information about objects and events in the environment.

In the same vein, Delos Santos (2022), pointed out that home language skills are transferable to new languages and strengthen children’s understanding of language use. It also contributes to child’s cultural growth, increase their vocabulary and communication skills and share valuable learning experiences.

Corollary, Montemayor (2020) stressed also that engaging children in conversation by the parents from an early age is essential for language development. While it may be a one-sided dialogue, parents should ask open-ended questions and wait for responses. As children progress, these conversations become more interactive and meaningful. Aside for this. Parents can create a language rich environment, engaging in responsive communication, reading aloud, expanding vocabulary, encouraging conversation, limiting screen time can greatly influence their child’s linguistic journey.

Table 6 presents the level of parental involvement in literacy development among kindergarteners along vocabulary development.

As gleaned from the table, the level of parental involvement in literacy development among kindergarteners along vocabulary development obtained an overall weighted mean of 2.75 described as “Moderately Involved”. All ten indicators have the same transmuted rating of “Moderately Involved” with weighted means ranging from 2.53 to 3.03.

This could be interpreted to mean that the parents considerably involved themselves in teaching their children on vocabulary especially in noting unfamiliar words that their children encounter, explaining vocabulary words with examples and counter examples, revisiting new words using context clues and fun activities to reinforce the words meaning and the use of word with variant meanings. The parents believed that these activities could help their children develop the vocabularies which are essential in reading.

Table 6. *Level of Parental Involvement in Literacy Development among Kindergarteners along Vocabulary Development*

<i>Vocabulary</i>		<i>WM</i>	<i>TR</i>
<i>As a parent, I involve myself in literacy development by</i>			
1.	helping note unfamiliar words that your child encounter	2.75	MI
2.	coming up with age-appropriate definitions	2.88	MI
3.	explaining vocabulary words with examples and counter examples	2.70	MI
4.	revisiting new words	2.85	MI
5.	using fun activities to reinforce the words meaning	2.78	MI
6.	using context clues	2.53	MI
7.	using words with variant meanings	2.63	MI
8.	emphasizing the connections among words	2.75	MI
9.	exposing my child to the same word many times to support learning	3.03	MI
10.	using graphic organizers to define new words	2.58	MI
OWM		2.75	MI

Legend: 4.50-5.00 – Highly Involved (HI); 3.50-4.49 - Involved (I); 2.50-3.49 - Moderately Involved (MI); 1.50-2.49 - Slightly Involved (SI); 1.00-1.49 - Not Involved (NI)

The essence of parental involvement in vocabulary development among children can not be underestimated considering that this is important in reading. According to Thompson & Galindo (2017), a robust vocabulary improves all areas of communication, listening, speaking, reading and writing. Vocabulary is critical to child’s success for these reasons. Vocabulary growth is directly related to school achievement. The size of a child’s vocabulary in kindergarten predicts the ability to learn to read. Vocabulary is also essential in record and foreign language acquisition because without its appropriate and sufficient knowledge, learners cannot understand others or express their own feelings.

Corollary, Gao & Nang (2017) stressed that learners instinctively recognize the importance of vocabulary to their language learning. Young children carry grammar books no that teaching vocabulary helps them understand and communicate with others in a very

successful way. Aside from this, it can deepen knowledge of word meanings and help students understand what they are hearing or reading. It can also help them use word's accurately in speaking and writing.

Table 7 presents the level of parental involvement in literacy development among kindergarteners along words and patterns.

Table 7. *Level of Parental Involvement in Literacy Development among Kindergarteners along Words and Patterns*

<i>Words and Patterns</i>		<i>WM</i>	<i>TR</i>
<i>As a parent, I involve myself in literacy development by</i>			
1.	reading books that have repetition	2.83	MI
2.	singing songs that have repetition	2.98	MI
3.	describing my child's actions to the songs that I sing	3.03	MI
4.	creating a pattern and have them copy it	2.80	MI
5.	going on a nature walk	2.90	MI
6.	searching the patterns at home	2.85	MI
7.	looking for patterns in nature	2.80	MI
8.	introducing each new words one at a time	2.75	MI
9.	saying the word aloud and have my child repeat the word	2.98	MI
10.	encouraging my child to discover patterns in reading and writing	2.88	MI
OWM		2.88	MI

Legend: 4.50-5.00 – Highly Involved (HI); 3.50-4.49 - Involved (I); 2.50-3.49 - Moderately Involved (MI); 1.50-2.49 - Slightly Involved (SI); 1.00-1.49 - Not Involved (NI)

As seen in the table, the level of parental involvement in literacy development among kindergarteners along words and patterns obtained an overall weighted mean of 2.88 denoting a “Moderately involved” transmuted rating. This considerable involvement of parents along this area could be attributed to the inadequacy of learning materials and lack of knowledge of parents on the use words ad patterns in literacy considering that most of the parents have only attended the secondary level of basic education.

It is highly noted also that all of the ten indicators obtained a transmuted rating of “Moderately Involved” having weighted means that range from 2.75 to 3.03. This would mean that the parents are fairly involved in teaching their children in all the skills focusing words and patterns.

As there a need to encourage parents to get highly involved in teaching their children at home on the basic rudiments of literacy development particularly on words and patterns considering this is essential for children to learn reading and have comprehension.

According to Topor (2020), learning word patterns help students in phonics which is the process of learning how to read using sounds of single letters. As children begin to study word patterns, they start with simple words that have basic sequences. Teaching word patterns is important for students to effectively learn how to read.

Moreover, Verma (2019) stressed that word study provides students with opportunities to investigate and understand the patterns in words. Knowledge of these patterns means that learners need not learn to spell one word at a time. On the other hand, patterns help children make predictions as they begin to understand and anticipate what comes next.

Table 8 shows the summary result of the level of parental involvement in literacy development among kindergarteners.

Table 8. *Summary of the Level of Parental Involvement in Literacy Development among Kindergarteners*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>TR</i>
1. Alphabet knowledge	2.97	MI
2. Phonological Awareness	2.83	MI
3. Print Concepts	2.81	MI
4. Word and Patterns	2.88	MI
5. Vocabulary	2.75	MI
6. Language Development	3.00	MI
OWM	2.87	MI

Legend: 4.50-5.00 – Highly Involved (HI); 3.50-4.49 - Involved (I); 2.50-3.49 - Moderately Involved (MI); 1.50-2.49 - Slightly Involved (SI); 1.00-1.49 - Not Involved (NI)

As reflected in the table, the grand overall level of parental involvement in literacy development among kindergarteners obtained a weighted mean of 2.87 denoting a transmuted rating of “Moderately involved” where language development ranked the highest with an OWM of 3.00. This could be interpreted to mean that the parents involvement considerably help their children in language learning which respond to their children to communicate and use different words in different context. In this case, they can also empower their children to learn independently, thus making them learn at their own pace.

Further, as noted in the table that parents involvement in vocabulary obtained the lowest OWM of 2.75. This could mean that parents have different knowledge in teaching their children along said area considering their educational attainment. In as much as most of them attended the secondary level of basic education, their knowledge in the aspect of vocabulary development is limited. So they can only involve themselves to the skills that they know that can help their children.

According to Dysart (2019), the need of parental involvement in teaching young children in vocabulary knowledge is very essential considering that vocabulary knowledge is the building block of learning a second language and the degree of success for learning any language depends on the amount of vocabulary a learner processes. It is also useful for developing knowledge and skills in multiple aspects of language and literacy. This includes helping with decoding, comprehension and also fluency.

Summary For Mean Difference In The Level Of Parental Involvement In Literacy Development Among Kindergarteners

Relative to the problems of this study which sought to determine the level of parental involvement to determine the significant difference of the level of parental involvement in literacy development among kindergarteners across their profile variables, the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used and computed and is indicated by F-Values with their corresponding significance level. This was done to make a more in depth analysis of the data gathered in this study, whereby the profile of the respondent parents was compared to their level of parental involvement in literacy development.

Table 9 presents the ANOVA with their corresponding values of significance.

Table 9. Mean Difference in Level of Parental Involvement in Literacy Development among Kindergarteners

<i>Profile Variables</i>	<i>Sources of Variation</i>	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
Highest Educational Attainment	Between Groups	14.994	4	3.749	7.751	.000
	Within Groups	16.928	35	.484		
	Total	31.922	39			
Occupation	Between Groups	9.361	6	1.560	2.282	.059
	Within Groups	22.561	33	.684		
	Total	31.922	39			
Family Monthly Income	Between Groups	10.073	5	2.015	3.135	.020
	Within Groups	21.849	34	.643		
	Total	31.922	39			
Number of Reading Materials at Home	Between Groups	7.246	3	2.415	3.524	.024
	Within Groups	24.676	36	.685		
	Total	31.922	39			

The summary table for ANOVA indicates the mean difference in the level of parental involvement in literacy development among kindergarteners across profile variables. Generally, most of the data indicate a difference among parents level of involvement in literacy development.

Therefore, the research hypothesis which states that there is significant difference in the level of parental involvement in literacy development among kindergarteners across the profile variables, highest educational attainment, monthly family income, number of reading materials is accepted at .05 level of significance. These ANOVA results would mean that the means of all the groups are not equal. This means that their variation is different.

On the other hand, there is a significant difference in the level of parental involvement in literacy among kindergarteners across the profile occupation of parents. Therefore, the research hypothesis is rejected at .05 level of significance level. This indicates that there is a statistically significant difference among the groups being compared.

Table 10 presents the t-test results and their corresponding significance.

Table 10. T-Test Results and the Corresponding Significance of Profile Variables Sex and Number of Children

		<i>Levene's Test for Equality of Variances</i>		<i>t-test for Equality of Means</i>						
		<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Sig. (2-tailed)</i>	<i>Mean Difference</i>	<i>Std. Error Difference</i>	<i>95% Confidence Interval of the Difference</i>	
									<i>Lower</i>	<i>Upper</i>
Sex	Equal variances assumed	5.123	.029	.363	38	.719	.10492	.28934	-.48081	.69065
	Equal variances not assumed			.363	33.781	.719	.10492	.28934	-.48323	.69306
Number of Children	Equal variances assumed	.492	.487	.824	38	.415	.23957	.29057	-.34865	.82779
	Equal variances not assumed			.803	30.992	.428	.23957	.29826	-.36874	.84788

It can be gleaned from the table that the overall significant value indicators of .029 across the profile variable sex is lower than the significant value of .05 level of significance. This significant difference warrants the acceptance of the research hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the level of parental involvement in literacy development among kindergarteners. Indeed, this profile is significant in the involvement of parents in literacy development.

On the other hand, the significant value indicator of .487 across the profile variable number of children is higher than the significant value of .05 level of significance. This significant difference warrants the acceptance of the research hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the level of parental involvement in literacy development among kindergarteners across the aforementioned variable. Therefore, the profile variable number of children is not significant in parental involvement in literacy development. This could be interpreted as meaning that an effect or pattern exists.

Relationship Between The Level Of Parental Involvement In Literacy Development Among Kindergarteners

Table 11 shows the Pearson r correlation between the level of parental involvement in literacy development among kindergarteners.

Table 11. *Pearson R Correlation between the Level of Parental Involvement in Literacy Development among Kindergarteners*

<i>Profile Variables</i>	<i>Pearson Correlation</i>	<i>Sig. (2-tailed)</i>
Sex	-.059	.719
Highest Educational Attainment	.621**	.000
Occupation	-.232	.150
Family Monthly Income	.420**	.007
Number of Children	-.133	.415
Number of Reading Materials At home	.470	.002

It can be observed in the table that the Pearson-r values of the paired independent and dependent variables, sex, occupation, and the number of children do not have significant relationships to the respondents' level of involvement in literacy development among kindergarteners. In this regard, the research hypothesis which states that there are significant relationships between the aforementioned variables and the level of parental involvement in literacy development is rejected at .05 level of significance. In other words, the respondents' level of involvement in literacy development can't be affected by the aforementioned variables.

On the other hand, the profile variables highest educational attainment, monthly income and the number of reading materials indicate significant relationships having .000, .007 and .002 levels of significance. In the research hypothesis which states that there is a significant relationship between the level of parental involvement in literacy development among kindergarteners is accepted and .05 level of significance. As the profile variables highest educational attainment, monthly family income and the number of children are associated with parental involvement in literacy development among kindergarteners. This could mean that the higher the educational attainment of parents, the higher their involvement, the greater the income the more that they are highly involved. Likewise, the greater the number of their children, the more that they are involved in the education of their children.

Conclusions

In the light of the findings of this research, the following conclusions were formulated:

The respondent parents vary widely in their profiles and in certain instances, their variations are extreme.

The moderate level of parental involvement in literacy development among kindergarteners can be attributed to the inadequacy of learning materials at home and the low status of parents.

The respondent parents differ in their involvement in literacy development among their children.

The level of parental involvement in literacy development among kindergarteners can be associated with the profile variables highest educational attainment, monthly income and the number of children in the family.

Since vocabulary development obtained the lowest level of parental involvement in literacy development, concerned parents are encouraged to prioritize the needs of their children along this area considering that vocabulary development improved all areas of communication such as listening, speaking, reading and writing.

The respondent parents are encouraged to allocate specific time management in teaching their children in language development at home.

The respondent parents are encouraged to improve their level of involvement in literacy development by updating themselves on the different activities in literacy that could help their children for better performance in reading.

Concerned parents should also strengthen their partnership with teachers through initiatives such as parent-teacher workshops to build a sense of belonging and connection to the school, ultimately leading to their children's academic success.

The respondent parents are also encouraged to tie up with stakeholders for the provision of reading materials at home.

Further studies should be conducted on the wider scope of parental involvement in literacy development among kindergarteners.

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